

OPINION OF B.ED. STUDENTS ON ONLINE EDUCATION

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Introduction:

Nowadays the field of education is adjusting with new situations. From school education up to college education for the purpose of teaching and learning technology is being used. Due to pandemic situations, face to face learning has been replaced by online teaching - learning. Students and teachers are adopting and accommodating with these new changes. It is also a fact that although we are using technology for teaching purposes there is an absence of a clear pedagogical framework for online teaching - learning and evaluation. Various online platforms are used by the educational institute to carry out online education e.g. ZOOM Meeting, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, Whatsapp groups, telegram, Webex meet, Moodle, and so on.

The study is a small effort to understand the online scenario of teaching - learning through opinion of B.Ed. students. It will help educators to understand the pros and cons of online learning also, it will help to understand practical difficulties during online learning.

Significance of the study:

For the present study the researcher has taken the opinions of B.Ed. students about online education they are experiencing. They are practically involved in it, not only this but some colleges are conducting practice lessons also by using online platforms. Once we study the practical aspects of online education and think about learning and learning difficulties, we can develop a pedagogical framework for online education. Also, this study is important to develop protocols, etiquettes and netiquettes for online education.

Objectives of the study: For the present study the researcher has formulated following objectives.

1. To take an opinion of B.Ed. students about their experiences of online learning.
2. To study the practical difficulties of online education experience by B.Ed. students.
3. To suggest the solutions for creating an effective environment for online education.

Methodology ,Sample and Tools:

For the present study the researcher has used online survey methodology. The researcher has developed an opinionnaire by using Google forms. The same is circulated through online platforms like whatsapp, gmail, and other social networking sites. There were 20 items in the google form related to online education.

For the present study only students pursuing B.Ed. courses during the academic year 2019-21 are considered. Total 257 responses are received by the researcher. Students from University of Mumbai and SNDT Women's University participated in the survey.

Statistical Techniques used:

For the analysis of the data simple statistical tool i.e., percentage is used. and data analysis is presented in the form of graphs.

Analysis of the Data:

Following is the graphical analysis of the data.

1

which device do you prefer for on line Education?

257 responses

2

Difficulties faced by you during online learning

257 responses

3

What do you most like in online learning ?

257 responses

4

According to you online education is most suitable for:

257 responses

5

Which Examination pattern do you like for assessment of your learning ?

257 responses

6

online learning is beneficial for students

257 responses

7

Which Type of Learning do you prefer in future?

257 responses

8

Do you think that there is less interaction between student & Teachers in online learning ?

257 responses

9

Which things in traditional leaning you miss in online learning ?

257 responses

10

All students are actively involved in online learning

257 responses

11

How Much time are you willing to spend for online learning?

257 responses

12

Do you think that performance of same teacher differs in online & traditional teaching ?

257 responses

13

Do you think that proper orientation for students about online learning is required for better learning ?

257 responses

14

Do you think that techno savvy students will learn better than non techno savvy students in online learning ?

257 responses

Do you think that online education can replace traditional education in near future ?

257 responses

Important finding of the Study: Total 257 students participated in the survey. Following are the important findings of the study.

1. Majority of the respondents were from backgrounds of Arts faculty (64.6%) and 20.6% students from faculty of Science.
2. 80.5% students use their smartphone for the purpose of online education whereas 17.5% students use laptops for online education.
3. The data revealed that ZOOM and Google meet are the most popular online platforms being used by educational institutions. A little percentage is there of using WebEx meet and Google classroom.
4. Network issue is the major hindrance in online education reported by the students. Power failure, and management of time is also an issue for some students. A little number of students are not used to how to use online platforms effectively.
5. 70.4% percent of student's online education because it saves time and energy of traveling.36% also reported that they are comfortable learning from home. Students also revealed that they can submit their assignment at their own pace is a big advantage of using an online platform.
6. According to student's online education is most suitable for higher education.
7. 60% students prefer both the examination patterns i.e. online and offline written examination.
8. 33% students strongly agree that online education is beneficial 59.8% students are yet undecided about benefits of online learning.
9. 85.2% student's opinion that in the future also they will go with online and offline both education systems.11.3% students opinion that they are comfortable with offline systems only.
10. 64.2% students said that there are restrictions on student teacher's interaction during online education. 12.8% students are satisfied with the online student-teacher interactions.

11. 54.1% students said that they are missing the interactions with their classmates.45.9% students are missing the learning environment.
12. 74.7% students do not agree that all the students participate in online interactions.25.3% students are satisfied with the participation of active engagement of the students.
13. 39.7% students said that online education should not be more than two hours.27.6% students said that it should be less than two hours.
14. 45.1% of students think that a teacher's performance is different in online classes than traditional face to face teaching. 22.1% of students do not agree with this.
15. 61.1% students said that an institution should provide orientation about online platforms to make the learning process effective.
16. 33.5% students think that students who know technology will perform better whereas 13.2% students do not agree with this. Rest of the students are undecided.
17. 74.7% students have used digital classrooms for learning, they are familiar with this.
18. 68.9% students have used online platforms for examinations.
19. 53.7% of students have completed an online course during the lockdown period.
20. 21.4% students think that online education is a good option for traditional face to face learning.28.8% students think that only face to face learning is a good option.49.8% students are undecided about this.

Suggestions: on the basis of above findings following suggestions can be given.

1. Educational institutes should provide the orientation of online platforms to the students.
2. Along with real time online platforms digital classrooms must be used.
3. Teachers should focus on maximum student - teacher, student- student interactions.
4. Government should provide internet data plans to students at concessional rates.
5. Educational institutions can also subscribe to internet plans at concessional rates for their students.
6. There should be awareness about physical posture, protection of eyesight during use of dental devices.
7. Mind-set of the students should be developed for both the online and offline platforms for the future.
8. As there are problems of electricity failure, management of the time so educational institutes should provide recordings of the lectures.
9. Continued evaluation should be done to understand learning of the students.
10. Teachers should take continuous feedback from students regarding their expectations, difficulties during online education.
11. Students who are facing problems in online education may get frustrated , so teachers should provide counselling to them.

Conclusion:

We are living in an age of technology; judicious use of technology can make wonders in the field of education. No doubt that face to face learning is best but for the future as online education is convenient; we should use both the platforms adequately. It is also necessary to develop a pedagogy for online learning to make it more effective.

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